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Work Package 9

Microbiomics data analysis

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Project Deliverable

D9.3: Ontology and semantic metadata for metagenomic profiles and tools for NGS data management

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes how to manage metagenomics data in the HEAP technical platform. It provides the data model representing semantics to access metadata about metagenomics experiments. The model provides the necessary components to cover the data cycle from samples to analysis results.

The HEAP metagenomics data model follows the omics metadata model from the EHEN Metadata Working Group, subgroup: omics.

This deliverable also describes the metagenomics pipelines implemented in the HEAP platform available to the researchers from HEAP and EHEN.

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1 Introduction

The HEAP Microbiomics data analysis work package (WP9) provides analysis tools for knowledge discovery about microorganisms and diseases.

What is Microbiomics?

The microbiome is the community of microorganisms living inside a host. It comprises bacteria, fungi, archaea, and even viruses. Microbiomics is the science of collectively identifying, characterising, and studying microorganisms in their habitats. What microorganisms are present, how they interact, how they replicate, and how they can be associated with disease, are some of the questions covered in the microbiomics field. Microbiomics analysis has enabled us to study these communities in their natural habitat, thereby revolutionising our knowledge of host-associated microbes and reconceptualizing our definition of "human."

(<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33226670/>)

What are Metagenomics and Metatranscriptomics?

Metagenomics is the field comprising studies on non-host genomics. If we are to analyse a human specimen, metagenomics will investigate all DNA present in the specimen that is not human. DNA can belong to bacteria, fungi, archaea, and viruses. Metagenomic analysis of DNA tells what DNA organisms are present and provides molecular characterisation.

Metatranscriptomics is related to the RNA present that is not related to the host. Following the same example of a human specimen, metatranscriptomics will provide information about RNA organisms (metagenomics cannot identify RNA viruses for example), as well as those whose genome is a DNA molecule but that is transcribing (replicating).

Both fields are of high importance, as some microorganisms can “just” be present (DNA), but not replicate (RNA). For human cancers with a microorganism agent aetiology, RNA presence is a must.

The WP9 is focused on metagenomics and metatranscriptomics analyses of DNA/RNA sequences from samples from different datasets in the HEAP Information Commons (IC). At this moment, we analyse data from TCGA [2] (a well-known and validated public database “The Cancer Genome Atlas”, <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>), the Swedish cervical screening cohort (comprising more than 0.5 million specimens from women invited to the organised screening program in Sweden), the Finnish Community Randomised trial of HPV Vaccination, which originally involved 80 000 adolescent boys and girls and the Finnish Maternity Cohort dataset of about 1 million Finnish women with linkable diseases associations available.

This deliverable includes three main sections:

- Metadata model for metagenomics profiling of the samples
- Metagenomics pipelines developed by WP9
- Future work

2 Ontology and semantic metadata for metagenomics profiles

2.1 The HEAP metagenomics data model

The work developed by HEAP focuses on using the existing concepts and categories involved in the metagenomics domain that can represent the relevant properties and relations necessary for manage and analyse data from the HEAP cohorts and produce metagenomics knowledge.

Due to the HEAP involvement in the EHEN metadata working group, we have reused our contribution to the EHEN model and customised it for the metagenomics domain. This strategy will facilitate the sharing of metagenomics metadata with the EHEN community.

The data model has nine main entities. HEAP implements the model by taking the sample as a central entity. However, the main aim of the model is to provide the correct semantics to make possible the query and sharing of data inside the HEAP platform, through the HEAP external catalogue, and through the EHEN catalogue.

Entities and values lists in the data model follow the MABIS standard (Minimal Information About Biobank data Sharing) as much as possible.

Entity	Attribute	Description	Level
Study	StudyID	PUI of the Study (project)	Mandatory
Study	Study name	Study name	Mandatory
Study	Study Acronym	Study Acronym	Optional
Study	Description	Study Description	Mandatory
Study	Principal Investigator	Principal Investigator Name	Mandatory
Study	Keywords	list of Keywords separated by comma	Mandatory
Study	Study design	Design of the study	Optional
Contact Person	First Name	First Name of the contact person	Mandatory
Contact Person	Last name	Last name of the contact person	Mandatory
Contact Person	Email	email of the contact person	Mandatory
Contact Person	Research ID	ORCID, LinkedIn, etc.	Optional
Contact Person	Institution	Name of institution	Mandatory
Contact Person	website	Institution website	Mandatory
Cohort	CohortID	DOI or other persistent ID	Optional
Cohort	Cohort Name	Name of the cohort as approved	Optional
Cohort	Cohort Description	Descriptive text	Optional
Sample	Sample type	Sample type following MIABIS*	Mandatory
Sample	Sample diagnostic	ICD10 disease code	Optional
Sample	Sample size	Number of samples	Optional

Subject	Sex	Sex according to MIABIS	Optional
Subject	Age max	Max age range	Optional
Subject	Age min	Min age range	Optional
Subject	Category	sample donor category	Optional
Subject	Family member	Family member value	Optional
Lab Analysis	Omics experiment	Type of Omics experiment	Mandatory
Lab Analysis	Instrument	Name of instrument use for lab analysis	Mandatory
Lab Analysis	Experiment description	Descriptive text about the experiment	Optional
Lab Analysis	Raw data type	Data type value	Mandatory
Data Analysis	Type of Analysis	Description (free text)	Optional
Data Analysis	Software name	Description (free text)	Optional
Data Analysis	Software version	Description (free text)	Optional
Data Analysis	Link to software	GitHub, etc.	Optional
Data Analysis	File format	Data file format value	Mandatory
Data Analysis	Date	Date of the data analysis	Optional
Result	Result description	Description (free text)	Optional
Result	Publication	Link to publication	Optional
Result	Dataset	Link to dataset	Optional
Keyword	Keywords	List of keywords separated by comma	Mandatory

Predefine list values for implementing the data model:

List	List Value
Sample Type	Whole blood
Sample Type	Plasma
Sample Type	Serum
Sample Type	Urine
Sample Type	Stool
Sample Type	CSF
Sample Type	Nasal
Sample Type	Cervical swab
Sample Type	Cervical smear
Sample Type	Cervical cells
Sample Type	Saliva
Sample Type	Sputum
Sample Type	FFPE

Sample Type	Tissue
Sample Type	Tissue slide
Sample Type	Placenta
Sex	Female
Sex	Male
Sex	Other
Sex	Unknown
Family member	Mother
Family member	Father
Family member	Child
Family member	Sibling
Family member	Grandmother
Family member	Grandfather
Data Type	Image
Data Type	Structured data
Data Type	Unstructured data
Data File Format	txt
Data File Format	fastq
Data File Format	Bam
Data File Format	csv
Data File Format	m8
Data File Format	fasta
Data File Format	tab
Data File Format	sam
Omics Experiment	Epigenomics
Omics Experiment	Exposomics
Omics Experiment	Exomics
Omics Experiment	Genomics
Omics Experiment	Classical genetics
Omics Experiment	Lipidomics
Omics Experiment	Metabolomics
Omics Experiment	Metagenomics
Omics Experiment	Microbiomics
Omics Experiment	Proteomics
Omics Experiment	Transcriptomics
Category	Case
Category	Control

Category	Other
Study design	Case-control
Study design	Cohort
Study design	Cross-sectional
Study design	Longitudinal
Study design	Twin-study
Study design	Quality control
Study design	Population-based
Study design	Disease specific
Study design	Birth cohort
Study design	Other
Study design	In vitro
Study design	Animal model

This data model is being implemented into the HEAP platform so it can be used by any dataset related to omics experiments and datasets from different cohorts can be combined to improve analysis results.

3 Metagenomics pipelines

As datasets are different, and scientists may have different research questions, the main objective for the WP9 is to provide pipelines for metagenomic (DNA) and metatranscriptomic (RNA) analysis that are user-friendly, open-source and generic. Researchers can easily use these pipelines and bioinformatic tools for different research purposes and with different datasets.

3.1 HPV-meta

The research team from Karolinska led by Sara Arroyo Muhr provided an open-source bioinformatics pipeline, “HPV meta”, that aims to detect HPV transcripts in RNA sequencing data, including several steps to warn operators of possible viral contamination.

The “HPV-meta” pipeline automatically performs several steps:

1. pre-processing of the sequencing files (quality trimming and human genome filtering),
2. HPV detection using non-human high-quality reads (blastx),
3. post-analysis that includes both the cut-off settlement (validation, 10 reads and 690 bp coverage to make an HPV call)
4. fasta sequence generation for HPV positive samples.

The **Tasta** sequence is intended for users to inspect possible contamination (high sequence identity among specimens), which is a non-very rare occurrence in next-generation sequencing and may have a terrible impact, such as compromising public databases.

Figure 1 provides the workflow for the HPV-meta pipeline:

All steps used in the pipeline implement open-source tools (trimmomatic, nexgenmap, samtools, diamond, GATK) and several in-house scripts to automatise the workflow. The pipeline was tested and validated using the whole TCGA (the cancer genome atlas) database.

TCGA is a collaboration between the National Cancer Institute and the National Human Genome Research Institute and contains molecularly characterisation of over 20,000 primary cancers and matched normal specimens spanning 33 cancer types (<https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>, accessed on 2021-08-10). Using the GDC transfer tool, we downloaded 10,908 bam files comprising around 90 terabytes of sequencing data.

According to pipeline cut-offs, the “HPV-meta” pipeline identified 488 HPV-positive specimens among the 10,904 bam files (4.5%). It detected a total of 25 different HPV types among the studies included within the TCGA, with HPV 16 (261/488), HPV18 (72/488) and 38 (41/488) being the types most commonly found. For some cancer forms, like cervical cancers, it is already known that they will regularly contain HPV transcripts from the E6 and E7 viral oncogenes, and these cancer forms did serve as a positive control in this project. Organs with HPV-associated cancers showed the highest number of specimens positive for HPV as expected (cervix uteri (n=291/309), endometrium (n=45/561) and tonsils (n=34/41)). HPV was also detected in non-HPV-associated tumours (e.g. 7/683 cerebrum/brain tumours).

To validate the results, we examined all original bam files from the TCGA as they had the HPV mapping information and compared those results with the results from “HPV-meta”. There was almost a 100% agreement (99.98%), with only 2/488 HPV-positive samples not reporting the same genotype. The disagreement of one of them (cervical tumour) could be explained due to multiple infections of 2 genotypes presenting the same number of reads in the same sample. The second disagreement occurred in one ovarian tumour where two different non-officially HPVs were reported. While the type detected in the original bam files corresponded to HPV-mCG3 (non-official HPV sequence submitted in 2012), the “HPV-meta” revealed the presence of HPV-mSK041 (non-official HPV sequence submitted in 2018, and therefore not present in the original database). It can thus confirm that “HPV-meta” could detect all HPVs with no obstacle.

Possible contamination within samples has already been reported for TCGA specimens (HPV 38 in endometrial samples and HeLa nucleic acid contamination leading to misidentification of HPV 18 in non-cervical cancers). In agreement with these authors, HPV 38 was detected in 41 samples, and all of them belonged to the same study (endometrium), which should cause at least suspicion about possible contamination (Figure 2). Fasta-generated alignments and pairwise comparisons showed total sequence identity among most sequences (> 80%) for HPV type 38, raising a flag for possible contamination. The same scenario occurred in some TCGA studies for HPV 18 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Pairwise comparison of HPV fasta files

The “HPV-meta” is an open-source pipeline which accurately detects HPV in RNA sequencing data with validated cut-offs. The produced fasta file makes it possible to investigate contamination, a non-very rare occurrence in next-generation sequencing which should always be considered.

The code is publicly available (<https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta>). It is implemented in the Spark and Hadoop environment, but it can also be used in other environments. The pipeline is fully implemented in HEAP Hopsworks, and its detailed description can be found in the journal Nature, Scientific Reports in July 2022 [1].

3.2 Biopipeline

The research team from Karolinska, provided another open-source bioinformatics pipeline, “Biopipeline”. This pipeline performs a taxonomy classification of all the non-host genomes in one specimen. It performs the identification and classification of bacteria, viruses and fungi, which is the output of the pipeline.

Based on the same principles (user-friendly, open-source and generic), the pipeline provides tools that the researcher can use partly or fully. It includes three main steps: pre-analysis, taxonomic classification, and post-analysis.

The pre-analysis is the same as in the HPV-meta described above (Figure 1), including the quality trimming and the human sequences removal. After performing the pre-analysis tools, the user can select “taxonomic classification”, which is performed by the well-known open-source software Kraken 2, instead of Diamond_HP_V_db (See Figure 3)

Figure 3: Description of Biopipeline’s flow.

After the analysis is done by Kraken, the post-analysis tool will provide the taxonomy classification, relative abundance, and alpha and beta diversity of the microorganisms detected in the specimen.

The Biopipeline is partly implemented in the HEAP platform, with all the steps needed except for the post-analysis scripts. The next step is to implement the post-analysis inside HEAP platform once R studio is integrated.

The Hopworks team (WP6) is providing support to implement all the analysis tools into the HEAP platform. One relevant feature is the integration of R studio which will make it possible to execute R analyses tools developed by HEAP partners and by the exposome research community.

During the BYOD event held in Stockholm in November 2022, the partners from Finland and Stanford tested Biopipeline with their own datasets. The BIO-pipeline was validated using the TCGA database, a sub-dataset (800 samples) of the cervical screening cohorts, colorectal specimens from the TCGA, data from the Swedish research studies in immunosuppressed patients. In early 2023 we will submit a manuscript describing the whole pipeline for publication.

3.3 Machine Learning methods for HPV detection

The Institute Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) at the University of Warsaw, led by Piotr Bala, provided an HPV prediction tool using Machine Learning for the classification of HPV virus based on the viral DNA/RNA sequence. The model is implemented in Hopsworks as described in deliverable D9.2.

3.4 CSC microbial pipeline

The research team from Finland led by Ville Pimenoff provided a bioinformatics pipeline, “CSC pipeline”, that comprehensively classifies microbial taxa and functional groups in metagenomes and meta-transcriptomes (3,4,5). It can be used both in DNA and RNA sequencing data, with certain caveats for RNA. The pipeline involves the pre-processing of the raw sequence data, the removal of human derived reads if necessary, the detection of microbial taxa and their functional groups, normalisation of the detection and plotting of the compositional diversity and distribution analysis.

Figure 1 provides the workflow for the CSC pipeline:

A concise summary of the workflow in its most important steps is below

- Preprocessing: Single or pair-end FASTQ -files are taken as input files. FASTQ-file is a file type typically provided by most current sequencing methodologies. FASTQ-files are quality trimmed including deduplication of likely PCR biases using Cutadapt, Trimmomatic, Picard and BBtools. Only high-quality reads are retained.
- If human reads need to be removed, a user can choose to filter them out using a fast kmer based filtering or mapping of human reads using bwa or bowtie.
- Classification of the high-quality reads: Pre-processed single or paired-end metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequences are classified using two different classifiers: Kraken2 (a k-mer matching algorithm) and MetaPhlan2 (a marker-gene mapping algorithm) with a large curated reference database for bacteria, virus, fungi, protozoa and archaea available (build in December 2022). Microbial functional groups are classified using HUMAnN2 algorithm.
- Quality control and normalisation: Output of classification of taxa and functional groups is checked for likely environmental contamination and outliers in the dataset. Further data normalisation and transformation for compositional analysis is performed.
- Results estimations and plotting: Distribution of microbial taxa across the dataset and stratified diversity estimations are plotted using R and further used for likely phylogenetic inference of particular microbial taxa.

This pipeline has already been used to validate and analyse microbial taxa from human stool and gut biopsies (Mas-Lloret et al. 2020, Obón-Santacana et al. 2022) and oral/cervical swab samples (Pimenoff et al. 2023). The pipeline and tools are available in the CSC computational environment and

soon also available in GitHub in order to be open-source. Work is to be done to implement the pipeline into Hopsworks.

During the BYOD event held in Stockholm in November 2022 the pipeline was available to HEAP partners to test at the CSC cluster, and the partners from Finland and Stanford validated in parallel their pipelines confirming the coherent results and use for parallel pipeline analysis for the exposome wearable dataset. The CSC pipeline has already been validated using a large colorectal cancer dataset (1600 samples) and the cervical cancer study using this pipeline will be published in early 2023. Implementation in Hopsworks is to be performed immediately.

4 Summary

The metagenomic pipelines and machine learning algorithms provided by the WP9 are user-friendly, open-source and generic tools that researchers can reuse and adapt for their data analysis.

During 2022, the Karolinska team has provided tools for HPV detection and taxonomic analysis. The pre-analysis step is generic. Any researcher performing sequencing analysis can use it to ensure high-quality data. In 2023, the group aims to develop and validate more bioinformatic tools within Hopsworks 3.0, targeting novel discovery and machine learning models for disease and cancer prediction.

During 2022, the Finnish team including CSC has provided computational resources and pipeline for comprehensive microorganism detection and analysis. The pipeline is flexible for parameter adaptation for different type and quality of metagenome and meta-transcriptome datasets. In 2023, the Finnish team aims to implement the pipeline also into Hopsworks 3.0 as well as to make it open-source, targeting comprehensive discovery and machine learning inferences for disease and cancer prediction.

The Institute Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) provided a Machine Learning model for classifying the HPV virus based on viral DNA/RNA sequences. The model was implemented in Hopsworks and trained and tested with TCGA specimens already subjected to the pre-analysis step. Currently, the team will focus on testing the model with raw data (human sequences included) and a different dataset (2400 cervical screening samples). If the model can predict HPV in the whole sequence, it means that the model can be trained with short sequences (no human sequence). It is relevant considering that training the model with long sequences is computationally intense and requires many resources and time.

Testing pipelines with different datasets helps to validate and improve the pipeline toward more accurate results.

Future plans include “tweaking” the algorithm for cancer prediction. HPV is known to cause cervical cancer, but that doesn’t mean everyone positive for HPV, will develop cancer. With

the large cervical screening cohort from Sweden, HPV status and the patient metadata, the aim is to predict who will develop cancer.

5 References

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